

Deliverable 1.1.1 - Current cataloging standards and practices

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¹ CRediT taxonomy <https://credit.niso.org/implementing-credit/>

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ROYAL MUSEUMS OF ART AND HISTORY
KONINKLIJKE MUSEA VOOR KUNST EN GESCHIEDENIS
MUSÉES ROYAUX D'ART ET D'HISTOIRE

Executive Summary

Essentially we have to integrate the data of the partners, make it available under a persistent identifier according to the FAIR data principles and maintain the integration throughout the operation of the MetaBelgica platform. Early on we identified the risk of disagreement when trying to maintain detailed information about authority records in a collaborative fashion. Therefore we decided to include only a minimal number of data fields for authority records, basically enough to disambiguate records. Concretely the name and name spelling variants of a person, identifier of the MetaBelgica partner institution, other international identifiers, birth and death date as well as birth and death place.

This deliverable presents the result of an internal survey about current cataloging practices at the Royal Library of Belgium (KBR), the Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium (RMFAB), the Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA) and the Royal Museums of Art and History (RMAH) for person and organization authorities and related dates and place information.

All institutions catalog authorities related to their collections. Names have to be catalogued, either fully bilingual in French and Dutch or depending on the cataloger they are catalogued in either French or Dutch or in some occasions in English. Additional information such as dates or placenames/countries are added if known. Dates are added in a standard notation, but that notation differs between the institutions. Additionally, no standard is used to encode uncertain dates. Placenames are only noted in textual form and possibly in a single language. Thus similarly to uncertain dates, the usage of standards would improve the current situation.

The envisioned Wikibase solution enables the standardized encoding of authority data and related dates and places. Hence overcoming certain limitations of some of the institution's current catalog systems. Additionally, the use of standards or conventions such as the use of ISNI identifiers for persons and organizations or the use of GeoNames for placenames decrease cataloging work and improve the quality and coverage of the data as multilingual labels can be fetched automatically without the need of manually cataloging all language variants. Multilinguality is also supported by the use of the Extended Date/Time Format for uncertain dates, because multilingual labels can be generated automatically based on a single language-independent EDTF notation, e.g. "18th century" in English or "18e eeuw" in Dutch. Please note that all partner institutions but KBR are currently undergo a migration to a new Content Management System (CMS) or will undergo a migration.

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1. Introduction

The goal of MetaBelgica is to combine the efforts of initially four Belgian Federal Scientific Institutes in terms of data management for authority data. Each institution has their own focus and collections, but due to the nature of the data there is an overlap of authority records. Yet this overlap is not explicitly annotated and additionally each institution uses their own authority management tools, data models and data curation guidelines.

This deliverable focuses on analyzing the current guidelines and standards used by the different partner institutions. It has the aim to distil common guidelines where possible or to make differences explicitly visible and to discuss them. So far, cataloging guidelines were only available for KBR, they were maintained internally but recently have been published under an open license (*Lowagie & Van Woensel, 2025*). However, the different partners follow some implicit guidelines or are in the process of migrating to a new system which requires them to recheck their guidelines anyway. Because mainly no guidelines were available to analyze, we instead asked 18 questions regarding cataloging.

Please note that information about the systems and data of the partners are available in a different deliverable focussing on data analysis (*Lieber et al., 2025*).

In section 2 we briefly discuss the currently used standards. In section 3 we discuss the answers to the internal survey and in section 4 we conclude. The appendix lists all questions and answers in full length.

2. Currently used standards

Each institution uses different management systems and data standards. Deliverable 1.2.2 (*Lieber et al., 2025*) provides more information on the systems and data from the partner institutions. In the following we briefly mention which standards are used and if guidelines are in place.

The prioritized datasets of all partner institutions follow a **MARC-based** standard and hence can be exported in XML format. For KBR, terms from the Resource Description and Access (RDA) framework are used in addition to textual input. KBRs current bilingual cataloging guidelines (*Lowagie & Van Woensel, 2025*) list which terms or values must be used. Data

from RMFAB and RMAH use the Categories for the Description of Works of Art (CDWA) standard. KIK-IRPA uses Adlib Museum software which is Spectrum compliant.

Earlier KBR cataloging guidelines from the 1960s focus on topics such as how names have to be spelled, how punctuation characters should be used or how links between library cards should be indicated and in which language (Liebaers et al., 1961). Because those guidelines come from a pre-computer era, we only consider the most recent and currently maintained RDA guidelines of KBR (*Lowagie & Van Woensel, 2025*).

3. Current guidelines

Because most partner institutions did not have readily available guidelines, but were in the process of explicitly writing them down, we used a simple survey based on 18 questions to gather relevant information. In this section we summarize the different answers per category and discuss their implications for MetaBelgica. The survey questions as well as the answers from each institution are listed in the appendix.

3.1 General authority cataloging

The general cataloging questions revolve around the scope of authorities, the volume as well as possible processes for keeping the data up to date.

Authorities at all partner institutions are created if they are linked to one of the collection items of the institutions. For RMFAB, the majority of artist authority records were initially created in a single effort around the year 2000, new artist records are added when a new art object record is added. This clearly defines a scope of the current data sources and hence can be used to explicitly state the initial scope of MetaBelgica.

The **number of new records per year** varies across institutions, but there are regular updates, for example when inaccuracies are noted by a curator or colleague or while working on a related exhibition or research project. A **yearly screening related to copyright** and works of public domain was mentioned by two institutions. This hints at the importance of the *date of death* field for contributors that can be used to determine the copyright status of a collection item. According to the answers it seems that records are often reviewed and checked **when being consulted for a concrete use case**. This hints at a possible added value of MetaBelgica: multiple curators/catalogers from different institutions will use the

integrated authority records in MetaBelgica, hence more reviews and checks are likely which positively influences the quality.

KBR is also an ISNI registration agency, hence the creation of new person authorities involves identifying and adding an existing ISNI identifier or requesting a new one.

3.2 Person entities

We discuss which data fields are mandatory, how to catalog alternate names and pseudonyms and which international identifiers are used.

When asked about **which data fields are mandatory**, most answers mention that at least a name as well as birth date and death date are mandatory (if known). Other answers either mention more fields (such as standard identifiers, nationality or place of birth and death) or less fields (only the type of authority). Subsequently, only the name is enforced by the respective management system for two of the institutions and nothing is enforced for the other two. Please note that this might change in the new Content Management Systems (CMS), all institutions but KBR are undergoing or will undergo a migration.

Alternate names and pseudonyms are curated by all of the institutions. Whether a pseudonym becomes a separate record varies across institutions. If separate records are used, usually they are linked. It has to be noted that in contrast to alternate names, the real name of a pseudonym is often not known and hence it should be a record on its own. The International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI) is actually assigned to each identity of a person, thus a pseudonym and the real name of a person (if known) get separate ISNI identifiers. Of course only if the person created anything under its real name. Within MetaBelgica we create authority records with their own persistent identifier, that are linked to local authority records of the partner institutions. This means that local guidelines and MetaBelgica guidelines with respect to identities do not necessarily have to align. For example, if a partner institution has separate records for identities of a person and MetaBelgica only has one, then each local identity can link to the same MetaBelgica entity and vice versa. Similarly, if a partner institution has one record for several identities of a person and MetaBelgica has multiple, then the single local identity can link to several MetaBelgica entities and subsequently different MetaBelgica entities can link to the same local record.

International identifiers are not always cataloged among the partners. KBR used to catalog VIAF and since KBR became an ISNI registration agency in 2020, systematically catalogs ISNI. RMAH uses ISNI among other standard identifiers, however, not systematically (16% of authorities have ISNI, see (Lieber et al., 2025)). Otherwise standard identifiers may be used to consult information without being cataloged.

For MetaBelgica we should not enforce too many fields as simply not all information might be available. For the scope of MetaBelgica we initially limit ourselves to a few data fields, sufficient enough to disambiguate persons. We will add names and alternate names. We can follow existing guidelines of adding birth and death dates if known and similarly adding birth and death place if known. Additionally, we have to investigate how we can reuse and standardize existing annotations about occupation from the different partner catalogues, because an occupation can be used to distinguish two person records that share similar names and even birth dates.

We definitely should catalog international identifiers. The choice for ISNI is obvious since KBR is an ISNI registration agency. However, records of the global ISNI database link to local records from registration agencies. This means that we cannot request new ISNI identifiers from within KBR for authorities that only exist at a partner institution as there would be no link to a KBR authority. That said, ISNI identifiers can be added for authorities that already have an entry in the global ISNI database or alternatively authorities that do not yet have an ISNI but which exist at KBR. Similarly to Wikidata, we can add properties for other identifiers in our Wikibase. But probably we should discuss which ones are the most promising ones for systematic cataloging such that we achieve an optimal linking with other relevant data sources. A promising candidate identifier is the RKD Artists identifier from the domain of visual arts² and the Union List of Artist Names (ULAN) from the Getty Research Institute³.

3.3 Organization entities

We discuss different types of organizations, mandatory fields, different languages and international identifiers.

Diverse types of organizations are cataloged among the different MetaBelgica partners. Both KBR and KIK-IRPA have records about publishing houses. Interestingly both institutions use a separate publisher register linked to actual authorities in the respective authority

² RKD identifier <https://www.rkd.nl/en/collection/digital-collection/rkdartists-as-linked-open-data>

³ ULAN identifier: <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/ulan/>

datasets. In the current CMS of RMFAB, organizations appear in the “former owners” list in the provenance section of a record, alongside personal names. In the future CMS, these entities will likely be managed as authority records. KIK-IRPA's authority list of organizations is very diverse and contains names of museums, libraries, churches, public administration buildings, cultural associations, private companies and so on. Similarly, RMAH has records about manufacturers, companies, cultural institutions, or embassies. Thus, also broader than “just” publishing houses.

There are not many guidelines in terms of **mandatory fields**. For KBR at least a name and a country need to be cataloged. For other institutions there are no guidelines or only the name is required. In contrast to (contemporary) persons, organizations often have different names for different languages, not just a different spelling. Some partner institutions aim for **fully bilingual organization records**. Equivalent translations are required for RMAH, similarly, at RMFAB one or two individuals enter a record to ensure full bilingualism and data consistency. In the future CMS of RMFAB, this workflow will be reviewed to determine whether an alternative approach would be more efficient or appropriate. For KIK-IRPA, French is currently considered the pivot language, Dutch is an equivalent. For KBR, multiple languages are possible and exist, but it depends on the language of the cataloger.

International identifiers are not systematically cataloged at the different MetaBelgica partners. Only occasionally identifiers are recorded. KBR is an ISNI registration agency, but besides person authorities, no other data was systematically aligned with the global ISNI database yet nor is it systematically added. There are differences in terms of how the identifiers are encoded. Whereas KBR catalogs the ISNI identifier with spaces, RMAH stores the ISNI URL.

Clear guidelines are needed for MetaBelgica, given the diverse type of organizations. It starts with the type of organization, after an analysis we should get a clear overview about the different types and standardize those too. Names should ideally be added for all official Belgian languages, given our ambition to become an authoritative source. Additionally, indicating a country might be necessary to disambiguate organizational branches. Organizations are complex since they can cease to exist, change their name or merge. To this regard, the MetaBelgica Wikibase offers many possibilities to express complex relationships. However, identifying the bare minimum in the guidelines is a future challenge also for data governance.

3.4 Dates

We discuss which date standards are used for both known dates and uncertain dates. Statistics about the usage of different date patterns can be found in deliverable 1.2.2 (*Lieber et al., 2025*).

At all MetaBelgica partners, dates are encoded following a standard notation, however, not the same. KBR follows the ISO-8601 standard with the pattern YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY that is used in MARC field 046. Similarly, RMFAB is using the YYYY variant of ISO-8601. KIK-IRPA follows the pattern YYYYMMDD and RMAH the pattern DD/MM/YYYY (displayed as DD.MM.YYYY). The ISO-8601 standard is not enforced at KBR which over time leads to various other ways to describe a date. Next to the MARC field 046, authority-related date information is also stored in MARC field 100\$d, those values were also extracted and standardized for MetaBelgica (*Lieber et al., 2025*).

Dates related to authorities are not always certain or not known at all. Especially for authority data related to previous centuries there are many unknowns. None of the institutions follow a standard for **uncertain dates**. For KBR it depends on the cataloger. At RMAH and RMFAB, a period with start and end date can be added in case the full date is not known. Additionally different variants of “circa” can be found in a free text field for remarks, which are then shown as suffixes. Similarly, at KIK-IRPA also a longer time period can be indicated if a date is uncertain, at KIK-IRPA an additional free-text field is used to specify why the date is uncertain. RMFAB, which is on the verge of implementing a new Collection Management System, is open to adopting standards that emerge from the MetaBelgica research. For KBR also no standard for uncertain dates is used, it depends on the cataloger. However, often there is a “flourish” date that indicates the period in which an author was active, based on known publishing dates. Thus also for KBR broader periods are indicated.

All partner institutions are in need of standardized dates. Initial desk research revealed that the Extended Date/Time Format (EDTF) is a good candidate to encode both certain and uncertain dates. Initially, this standard was developed at the Library of Congress, but it is part of ISO 8601 since the revision ISO 8601:2019 from March 2019. There is also technical support for EDTF in Wikibase via a plugin that was developed within the LUDAP project in Luxembourg. A similar project to provide authority data via Wikibase. Please note that **by using EDTF, also uncertain dates become multilingual**: An uncertain EDTF date like “[1820-02,1821-04]” can be displayed in different languages, for example “*between February 1820 and April 1821*” in English or “*Tussen februari 2020 en april 1821*” in Dutch.

3.5 Places

We discuss how placenames and countries are encoded as well as which languages are used.

All of the institutions catalog places and countries, however, besides a few exceptions for test purposes, none of the institutions uses international standards for placenames. KBR, KIK-IRPA and RMFAB use a notation where the placename is written in Dutch, English or French with an additional location in brackets, e.g. “Bergen (Norway)”. For KIK-IRPA the bracket notation will disappear in the next version of their thesaurus. At least for KBR and RMFAB the additional location in the form of a country is usually skipped if it is a Belgian placename. However, there are also exceptions as we have noticed in deliverable 1.2.2 (*Lieber et al., 2025*). The additional location can also be a region, e.g. “Montreal (Quebec)” for the Canadian city Montreal. At RMAH, two thesauri are used, one for the nationality and one for a date section. The former also includes historic territories, whereas the latter only includes contemporary countries. RMFAB follows more concrete conventions to indicate municipalities and French departments or US states: e.g.

- Municipality / Town (country, if not in Belgium)
- Municipality / Town, department/US state (country if not Belgium)

In terms of languages, for all institutions, except for the RMFAB, which operates bilingually in Dutch and French as default, there might be either French or Dutch and sometimes English. Often it depends on the language of the cataloger which is usually French or Dutch. For KIK-IRPA the pivot language is French and Dutch is an equivalent. At RMAH, thesauri-based fields should have values in French, Dutch and English, whereas for free-text fields it also depends on the cataloguer, thus French or Dutch. KBR experimented with the use of GeoNames URIs in MARC field 370, which is language independent, but can be used to obtain multilingual labels.

To achieve the FAIR goals of MetaBelgica, we should adopt a standard. At least for contemporary places, the online database GeoNames is a good candidate as it contains multilingual labels of placenames worldwide. For Belgian placenames the REFNIS dataset exists that also links to GeoNames identifiers. The features of the Wikibase platform enable us to encode multilingual labels directly in the Wikibase, initially those labels can be fetched from GeoNames. Adding such a semi-automatic multilingual support also supports the aim of MetaBelgica to become an authoritative source for Belgium. Including resolving one of

the largest gaps so far, the systematic support of the third official language of Belgium: German.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable has the aim to distil common guidelines where possible or to make differences explicitly visible and to discuss them. Because not every institution has readily available cataloging guidelines, we gathered information via an internal survey in the form of an online collaborative spreadsheet (see appendix for all questions and answers).

The provided answers to the general cataloging workflow questions sketch a reasonable scope for MetaBelgica and hint towards an added value. On the one hand, authorities of the current partner institutions are linked to their respective collections, hence **MetaBelgica authorities will be linked to at least one of the collections, which sets a scope**. Adding entities outside of this scope could raise questions for data governance, *who would be responsible for those records?* On the other hand, updating or correcting existing authority records at the partner institutions is often triggered when actively using the records for example for an exhibition or a research project. Currently if a KBR employee would improve an authority record in the KBR catalogue, the record would not be improved in the systems of the partners. But our envisioned shared management system and the authority overlap ensures that more catalogers and curators will look at the data and subsequently improve shared records if needed.

For person authorities the current guidelines in terms of mandatory fields largely overlap. Most institutions require at least a name and if known information about birth and death date and birth or death place. We can implement the same for MetaBelgica to ensure high quality data. Differences in local policies regarding how pseudonyms are cataloged, i.e. as additional fields in the real-name entity or as own entity, can be aligned with the MetaBelgica Wikibase. It remains to be discussed which policy we apply for MetaBelgica, but since for example ISNI identifiers are given per identity and that in a Wikibase we easily can add a link between a real-name entity and a potential pseudonym entity, we could choose a two-entity policy to create structured data.

For organizations we first have to determine what types of organizations are linked to our collections (publishers, manufacturers, etc). Especially for the large number of organisations

at KBR, we have to prioritise. Standardizing organization authority data will be the work of the coming months.

Standardized values for dates, places and countries are necessary to reach MetaBelgica's aims and enable its added value. The chosen platform Wikibase is able to represent the different use cases covered by the institutions and to provide this data in a FAIR manner. Standardized values obtained via deliverable 1.2.2 are already used to improve the local catalogs of the partner institutions (*Lieber et al., 2025*).

Last but not least, the usage of international identifiers is relevant for all kinds of entities, namely persons, organizations and places. Only via such a link can we easily obtain multilingual labels from other data sources or integrate our data into a larger European and international context.

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Appendix

A.1 General questions

1. When do you create an authority record? For example, does the authority need to be linked to at least x objects in your catalog? Does the authority need to be Belgian?

KBR: We create an authority record for every person or organization that contributes to a document that is related to the Belgian Bibliography, e.g. author, illustrator or other roles for persons or author or publisher for organizations.

KIK-IRPA: We create an authority record for every person or organization that contributes to a document, to a dossier or to a photo, but also for every person represented on / linked to the object present on our inventory and the most relevant persons mentioned on the documents and on the dossiers. It has to be linked at least to 1 object in our catalogues. The authority does not need to be Belgian.

RMFAB: An authority record is created for each artist whose (one or more) works belong to the RMFAB collections. Former owners are currently only archived in list format. This may be handled differently in the future (new CMS).

RMAH: An authority record is created for each object's author(s)/creator(s) and/or known former owner(s).

2. How many authority records do you roughly create per year? For example, is it in the nature of your collection policy to continuously update the collection and regularly add new authorities, or do you only occasionally create new authorities?

KBR: The different departments at KBR regularly create new authority records, for example we roughly receive 30,000 books each year via legal deposit, often from persons that debut and hence do not have an authority record yet. For example, roughly 21.000 person authorities were created in 2024, and roughly 15.000 in 2023 and in 2022.

KIK-IRPA: We continuously update the collection and regularly add new authorities.

RMFAB: We can guess an average of 100 per year but unfortunately we do not keep statistics on that, nor is it possible to get a quick view of it in a simple way. Not all artworks were already included in the online collection database. When a new record is entered, it is first verified whether the artist in question is already listed in the system as an authority. If this is not the case, this is the first thing that needs to be done. After that, the object record is addressed. So we can talk about a continuous update.

RMAH: New authorities are regularly created. The number of newly created authorities may vary from one year to another : while 176 were created in 2024, 393 were in 2023 and 568 in 2022.

3. Do you have processes/policies about updating/cleaning authority records? For example, do you regularly check your authorities for mistakes in a manual or automatic way?

KBR: On the one hand authorities are checked/updated as part of our tasks as ISNI registration agency, on the other hand, authority records are corrected/updated based on the progress/outcomes of research projects such as BELTRANS.

KIK-IRPA: Because of the high number of data entries, it is difficult to do regular checks. If we stumble upon an error, it is changed manually ad hoc. We do have guidelines for how to create entries for Persons and Institutions.

RMFAB: Each curator is responsible for a specific art collection and is therefore the appropriate person to inform the service responsible for updating the collection database (digital museum) if a particular attribution of an artwork needs to be changed, or an element of the authority record (birthplace/date, deathplace/date). Every year, the copyright information included in the artist authority records is updated for those artists whose works are in the public domain and the status of the SABAM entry is completed with the current year

RMAH: All controls and corrections over our authority records are done manually. Those edits can arise from preparatory work for an exhibition, research projects, colleagues remarks. Yearly, rights ownership of authorities are edited if they fall into the public domain. All Person authorities were manually controlled in 2023 but ideally it should become a yearly process supported by a designated workflow.

4. Please briefly sketch the workflow for the creation of an authority record?

KBR: KBR receives books via the legal deposit. Sometimes pre-records of MARC21-based document metadata are created based on our subscription to the databases boekenbank (Flanders) or Electre (French-speaking part of Belgium). In any case, a cataloger creates a new authority record for non existing contributors in our Library Management System Syracuse if the document is linked to the Belgian Bibliography and in case there is only a name in the document metadata. Monthly, new ISNIs are requested (or existing found) via an automatic lookup at the global ISNI database of recently added person authorities in the KBR catalog. Sometimes users of the OPAC catalog interface signal that we should add an ISNI for a specific person authority.

KIK-IRPA: N/A

RMFAB: The majority of artist authority records were created in a single effort around the year 2000. When a new art object record is now added and the artist is not yet represented, a new artist record is created at that time by one designated person. Currently, art object records are also entered by one or two individuals to ensure full bilingualism and data consistency. In the future, with the introduction of a new CMS, the workflow will be reviewed to determine whether an alternative approach would be more efficient or appropriate.

RMAH: As not all users of our CMS have access to the Author module, an authority record is created either if the authorship/ former ownership values have been added to free text fields of the object record or upon colleagues requests.

A.2 Person entities

This section lists questions related to cataloging guidelines with respect to persons.

5. Which data fields are mandatory for persons?

KBR: Mandatory (if known) are: name, ISNI or VIAF (024\$a), date of birth (046\$f), date of death (046\$g), nationality (370\$c). Certain birth/death years in MARC field 046\$f, possible uncertain dates in 100\$d, including flourishing dates

KIK-IRPA: Mandatory are (if known): name of author (if known), date of birth, date of death. Certain birth/death years have possible uncertain dates, including flourishing dates

RMFAB: Full name, Date and place of birth, Date and place of death

RMAH: Aside from the model type (Person, Culture or Institution), no field is required by the system for a record to exist.

6. Does the current system/workflow enforces the mandatory fields?

KBR: Only a name is mandatory, no other field is required by the system.

KIK-IRPA: Only a name is mandatory, no other field is required by the system.

RMFAB: No, should be reviewed in new CMS

RMAH: Even if the system does not make any fields mandatory, we ask, at the very least, for the "Name" field to be filled in according to the following format "Family name, Name". Initials are accepted for the name but the family name must be written in full.

7. Do you catalog alternate names and/or pseudonyms?

KBR: Yes, both alternate names and pseudonyms are cataloged. If someone only published under a pseudonym, this becomes the authority record, and the real name is added to the record if known.

KIK-IRPA: Both alternate names and pseudonyms are cataloged. If someone (author, artist, represented person or linked to an object are better known under a pseudonym, this becomes the authority record, and the real name is added to the record if known. When several pseudonyms or several forms of it, the most common becomes the authority.

RMFAB: Yes. Currently, name variants (including pseudonyms) are recorded in separate authority records that are linked to each other. In the future CMS, this will likely evolve toward a single record per artist, allowing all name variants to be catalogued within one entry.

RMAH: Yes, alternate names and pseudonyms are cataloged as well as current, full or other names or alternate spelling.

8. Do you create a separate record for an identity of a person, i.e. a pseudonym or do you add the pseudonym to the existing real-name of the authority?

KBR: Pseudonym information is usually stored in the record of the authority. However, there are exceptions in the KBR catalog for famous pseudonyms.

KIK-IRPA: Pseudonym(s) information is usually stored in the record of the authority.

RMFAB: A separate authority record is created for an alternative name/pseudonym. A link is made between both

RMAH: Pseudonyms are usually added to the existing real-name of the authority. If the authority is mostly known by their pseudonym, a record could be created for that identity and their real name would be added as "Other name".

9. Which international identifiers do you use for persons?

KBR: For persons we used VIAF and systematically start to use ISNI identifiers.

KIK-IRPA: We do not use specific international identifiers.

RMFAB: We don't use international identifiers yet but we do consult following databases in order to look up the preferred name or check the date of birth and death. RKDartists (Hollandse school), ULAN , BALAT.

RMAH: For persons we mostly use ISNI, LCNACO, ULAN and/or BNF.

A.3 Organization entities

This section lists questions related to cataloging guidelines with respect to corporate bodies.

10. For what types of organizations do you create authority records for?

KBR: Usually publishing houses or other institutions that can be authors. Apart from authority records for organizations, we also have a separate publisher-register where a publisher is linked to one or more authorities representing (branches of) this publisher. Authorities are also created for persons and organisations that have no role in the creation of the document, for example: former owner (abbays), donors (organisation that give their collection at KBR (Brailleliga, FOD BuZa, etc), dedicatees (a document is dedicated to...), or (less common) subject (a book about Rode Kruis, Rode Kruis as AORG can be added as subject in 610)

KIK-IRPA: Person names and institutions are both authority records in the same dataset. For example, usually publishing houses or other institutions that can be authors. Institutions are also related to the objects in our catalogue and to the content of the documents. Apart from authority records for organizations, we also have a separate publisher-register where a publisher is linked to one or more authorities representing (branches of) this publisher. Authorities are also created for persons and organisations that have no role in the creation of the object in the catalogue, for example: former owner (collections, churches, convents), donors o comitents and subject (representation on a photo or subject of a publication).

RMFAB: In the current collection database, organisations appear in list form under “former owners” in the provenance section, alongside personal names. In the future CMS, these entities will likely be managed as authority records.

RMAH: Due to the diversity of our collections, the catalogued organization (known to us as Institutions) are quite varied ranging from manufacturer, companies, cultural institutions, embassies, ...

11. Which data fields are mandatory for organizations?

KBR: Mandatory (if known) are: name (110\$a), country (371\$d)

KIK-IRPA: Name of the institution, code of the institution (we have a specific list of codes for each institution).

RMFAB: Organizations are primarily part of the documentary collection, which is managed by the library and archives in a separate database. They will not be implemented now, but ideally later on.

RMAH: Similarly to the Person type, no fields are mandatory in such but we require for the name of the organization to be filled in.

12. Which languages are mandatory for organizations?

KBR: No language is mandatory, the data is filled by the language of the cataloger, i.e. either Dutch or French, but some authorities also contain an English label. we can have different language-versions using subfield @ (\$@nl-BE and \$@fr-BE, eg: Baudouin, roi des belges - Boudewijn, koning der Belgen)

KIK-IRPA: Dutch and French. Currently French is considered the pivot language, Dutch is an equivalent.

RMFAB: N/A

RMAH: Due to the multilingualism aspect of our CMS, we ask to have equivalent translations of the values of "Name" field when relevant (e.g. for names/titles with different spelling depending on a language, companies' names, cultures' names)

13. Which international identifiers do you use for organizations?

KBR: So far we do not use standard identifiers for organizations, but we plan to use ISNI.

KIK-IRPA: We do not use specific international identifiers.

RMFAB: N/A

RMAH: International identifiers only have been occasionally used for organizations.

14. What are your encoding guidelines for international identifiers? For example, only the number, with or without spaces, a full URL, etc

KBR: The ISNI identifier is encoded with spaces in MARC field 024\$a based on this the related ISNI URI is added in MARC field 024\$1

KIK-IRPA: N/A

RMFAB: N/A

RMAH: The type (=Name) of the international identifier and the full URL are added when encoding international identifiers.

A.4 Dates

This section lists questions related to cataloging guidelines with respect to dates.

15. Which standards do you use for dates?

KBR: ISO-8601, but this standard was not enforced, thus over time also other forms were used, including different non-standardized variants. In MARC field 046 dates are usually YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY. However, the MARC field 100\$d also contains a single text representation of birth and death date, e.g. "1870-1921"

KIK-IRPA: YYYYMMDD.

RMFAB: YYYY

RMAH: If known, the full date is encoded as dd/MM/yyyy (displayed as dd.MM.yyyy). "Birth date" and "Death date" are usually created as individual "Date" types but the "Lifetime date" type also exists.

16. What are your encoding guidelines for uncertain dates?

KBR: Not standardized, depending on the cataloger. Especially in the MARC field 100\$d flourish dates are used when only publication dates of the persons are known. This is indicated either as fl. or flora. Dates might also be prefixed with different variants of circa.

KIK-IRPA: If a date is uncertain, choose a longer periode (ante quem - post quem). There is a free-text field remarks where you can specify why the date is uncertain.

RMFAB: The authority fields concerning year of birth and death should be completely revised. An initial sample shows that there are too many irregularities to speak of internal guidelines. In this sense, RMFAB is open to adopting suggestions that emerge from the research within Metabelgica and to clean up the data in this way before moving on to migration within the context of the new CMS.

RMAH: If the full date isn't known, either the date is encoded as a period from dd/MM/yy to dd/MM/yyyy covering the known month and/or year or the partial date is encoded as free text in the "Datation" field. Different variants of circa can also be found as remarks, then being displayed as suffixes.

A.5 Place names

This section lists questions related to cataloging guidelines with respect to place names.

17. Which standards do you use for place names and countries?

KBR: Place names are added as string values with the country in brackets. If it is a Belgian place name, the country is omitted. However, there are exceptions in the authority data. Testwise for some authorities geonames URIs are used in the MARC field 370.

KIK-IRPA: No standards were used for place names and countries. There are often "brackets" identifying the locaton, e.g. "Bruxelles[localité]" or "Bergen[Norway]". These brackets need to dissapear in the next version of the thesaurus.

RMFAB: No specific standard is used Conventions within RMFAB: Town (country, if not in Belgium), Municipality / Town (country, if not in Belgium), For France: Municipality / Town, department (France), Idem for USA

RMAH: Countries values may come from two different thesauri : one for the nationality of the authority and the other linked with the date section. The former also include some historic territories while the latter only include contemporary countries. Place names are encoded in a free text field linked to the date section.

18. Which languages are mandatory for place names and countries?

KBR: No language is mandatory, the data is filled by the language of the cataloger, i.e. either Dutch or French, but some authorities also contain an English label.

KIK-IRPA: French and Dutch. French is considered the pivot language, and Dutch is an equivalent.

RMFAB: NL, FR, EN

RMAH: For thesauri based fields, values should exist in French, Dutch and English. For free text based field, the data is filled in the language of the cataloger (either French or Dutch) therefore some places can be found in different languages throughout the records.